

Determinants of Job Satisfaction: Evidence from Indonesia

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Abstract:- The research aims to empirically prove the influence of organizational culture, work environment, and work motivation on job satisfaction. We use sampling technology using a total of 96 respondents in a population of 126 employees from the Jakarta local government. A multiple linear regression model is applied to estimate and analyze research hypotheses. The empirical findings of the study prove that the environment, culture, and work motivation both partially and simultaneously determine job satisfaction. This study was conducted with Other Service Providers and local officials of the DKI Jakarta Regional Wealth Management Agency, further studies may be conducted by other companies. No one has specifically investigated public officials from other private service providers (PJLPs) of the Jakarta Regional Wealth Management Agency.

Keywords:- Job Satisfaction, Culture, Motivation, Environment, Indonesia.

I. INTRODUCTION

Jakarta Provincial Government DKI has two types of staffing status, namely Employees with Civil Servant Status (PNS) and Non-Civil Servants (Non-NPS) namely other Service Providers of Individual Persons (PJLP). The Regional Asset Management Agency (BPAD) of Jakarta is an element of the implementation of the supporting function of government affairs in finance in the sub-field of regional asset management of Jakarta Province. Pre-research by observing data in the staffing section on job satisfaction of Employees of PJLP of DKI Jakarta Province to find out how many employees are dissatisfied and satisfied with the work they run from data in 2018 to 2019, could be seen by pre-research table on job satisfaction.

The job satisfaction of PJLP employees has decreased in their work and based on observation results of data in the staffing section, some problems experienced by Employees of PJLP related to factors that affect their job satisfaction include culture, environment, and motivation in the Regional Asset Management Agency of Jakarta province which is not good. The organizational culture at BPAD is not good because employees do not cooperate, especially in terms of communication in the framework of coordination of work that does not run smoothly, both due to the status of positions and employees who often avoid work so that it is difficult to contact, plus an inadequate work environment in supporting daily work activities such as air conditioners. The non-cold

and procurement of office equipment items are demands of employees. The condition of both conditions makes the employee's work motivation in work disturbed plus the lack of appreciation for employee services makes employee work motivation worse. Those are some of the problems that cause decreased job satisfaction experienced by employees of PJLP. The following is attached data on the factors that cause job dissatisfaction that can be summarized in this table of job dissatisfaction. The factors causing PJLP job dissatisfaction it is seen that from 2018 there was an increase in dissatisfaction, namely the work environment by 7%, work motivation by 8%, and organizational culture by 4%. These three variables affect the job satisfaction of PJLP in 2019, namely the work environment by 19%, work motivation by 19%, and the culture by 19%. Therefore, the author decided to study the effect of organizational culture, work environment, and work motivation on the job satisfaction of PJLP employees in BPAD DKI Jakarta Province

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. The Effect of Culture on Job Satisfaction

Culture is the norms that apply to companies that can determine employee behavior to complete work effectively and efficiently so that organizational goals can be achieved optimally. (Mulyana et al., 2022). Culture is a set of shared, self-evident, and tacit assumptions that determine how a group perceives thinks, and responds to its diverse environment (Kirkley et al., 2011)

Work fulfillment is the representative's sentiments about their work, regardless of whether cheerful or troubled because of worker communication with his workplace or as a view of mental demeanor, as well as the consequence of worker appraisal of his work (Sloan, 2007). Job satisfaction is a driver of employee and organizational outcomes because job satisfaction is the consequence of a representative's view of how well their work gives things that are thought of as significant (Mujahidin et al., 2021).

Organizational culture is a way that all members or members can cope with internal and external problems, so it is necessary to develop an organizational culture and educate the members to use it as a code of conduct for members when solving problems (Hapsari et al., 2021). The study of Riyanto et al. (2021a) proves that organizational culture positively affects job satisfaction. Reidhead (2020) said that it is revealed that there is a significant impact of organizational culture on

employee satisfaction. Reidhead (2020) found that organizational culture influences.

B. Effect of work environment on job satisfaction

A place with a group with multiple means of support to achieve the company's goals in line with the company's vision and mission (Endri et al., 2020). The work environment is something that exists in the worker's environment that can affect them in carrying out tasks such as temperature, humidity, ventilation, lighting, noise, cleanliness of the workplace, and whether or not work equipment is adequate (Virgiawan et al., 2021). A place for group gatherings with various supporting facilities can lead to employee job satisfaction (Endri et al., 2020). Workers want an environment that supports a conducive and comfortable work atmosphere, such as lighting, temperature, air circulation, noise, cleanliness, and the availability of work equipment (Virgiawan et al., 2021). Research conducted by Sanjaniet et al. (2022) said that the physical and non-physical work environment simultaneously affects job satisfaction. The empirical findings of Riyanto et al. (2021b) revealed that employee performance is influenced by a conducive and comfortable work environment.

C. Effect of Work Motivation on Job Satisfaction

Motivation is the driver of a person's behavior that encourages them to act in a way that is directed toward certain goals (Silitonga et al., 2020). Meanwhile, Tupti and Arif (2020) argue that motivation is a trigger for the spirit to work more productively and contribute positively to the company. Research conducted by Permana et al. (2021) found evidence that high work motivation can increase job satisfaction. Ali et al. (2016) found that work motivation can increase job satisfaction and employee performance. The research of Saluy et al. (2022) proves that work motivation has a positive effect on performance.

Fig 1:- Framework of Thinking

Based on previous research studies, the research hypothesis is as follows:

- H₁: Organizational culture has a positive effect on job satisfaction
- H₂: The work environment has a positive effect on job satisfaction
- H₃: Work motivation has a positive effect on job satisfaction;
- H₄: Organizational culture, environment, and motivation work together we have a positive effect on job satisfaction

III. METHODOLOGY

This study utilizes quantitative insight by utilizing quantitative correlational examination strategies. The correlational examination has the same importance as affiliated research. This study allows us to construct a theory that can explain, predict, and control symptoms. The technique that needs to be done in data collection techniques is using a questionnaire. The measurement scale in this study uses a Likert scale. Measurements are carried out using data that has been collected by giving a score which can be in the form of words, including; Strongly agree (5), Agree (4), Moderately Agree (3), Disagree (2), and Strongly Disagree (1). The research instrument using the Likert scale is made in the form of a checklist in the column of available options. The population in this study were all Individual PJLP at BPAD totaling 126 people, and the number of samples taken in this study was 95.8 or rounded up to 96 respondents.

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Thus the simple linear regression equation: $Y = 18.438 + 0.470X_1$, has a constant of 18,438 which can be stated that if the giving of organizational culture (X_1) is 0 then job satisfaction is 18,438. The regression coefficient of 0.470. It means every additional 1 organizational culture values contribute to increased job satisfaction of 0.470

Coefficients ^a					
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	18.438	2.466		7.475	.000
Organizational cultural	.470	.068	.583	6.959	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Job Satisfaction

Table 1:- Simple Linear Regression Analysis the Effect of Organizational Culture on Job Satisfaction

Thus the simple linear regression equation: $Y = 24.107 + 0.338X_2$, has a constant of 24,107 which can be stated if the work environment (X_2) is 0 and job satisfaction is 24,107. The regression coefficient of 0.338 states that an additional 1 work environment value contributes to increased job satisfaction of 0.338.

Coefficients ^a					
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	24.107	2.831		8.516	.000
Work Environment	.338	.085	.380	3.988	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Job Satisfaction

Table 2:- Simple Linear Regression Analysis the Effect of Environment on Job Satisfaction

Thus the simple linear regression equation: $Y = 23.290 + 0.370X_3$, has a constant of 23,290 which can be stated that if the motivation of work (X_3) is worth 0 then job satisfaction is

23,290. The coefficient value of 0.370 means that every increase in 1 work motivation value will provide an increase in job satisfaction of 0.370.

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	23.290	2.609		8.927	.000
	Work Motivation	.370	.079	.434	4.671	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Job Satisfaction

Table 3:- Simple Linear Regression Analysis between Work Motivation variables to Job Satisfaction

The calculation result of multiple regression analysis is obtained by the following formula:

$$Y = 15.911 + 0.367X_1 + 0.070X_2 + 0.123X_3$$

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	15.911	2.978		5.344	.000
	Organizational Culture	.367	.094	.455	3.894	.000
	Work Environment	.070	.089	.079	.788	.433
	Work Motivation	.123	.088	.144	1.400	.165

a. Dependent Variable: Job Satisfaction

Table 4:- Multiple Linear Regression Model Estimation

The equation informs that the tendency of change of each free variable to the bound variable can be inferred:

- The constant of 15,911 indicates that if the organizational culture (X₁), work environment (X₂), and work motivation (X₃), the values 0, then job satisfaction (Y), the value will be positive by = 15,911.
- Each increase of 1 score of organizational culture variables affects the increase in employee job satisfaction at BPAD by 0.367 scores assuming other variables are constant in value.
- Each increase of 1 work environment variable score affects the increase in employee job satisfaction at BPAD by 0.070 scores assuming other variables are constant in value.
- Each increase of 1 work motivation variable score affects the increase in employee job satisfaction at BPAD by 0.123 scores assuming other variables are constant in value.

Model Summary ^b				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.598 ^a	.358	.337	6.215

a. Predictors: (Constant), Organizational Culture, Work Environment, Work Motivation
b. Dependent Variable: Job Satisfaction

Table 5:- Multiple Determination Coefficient Test

Based on the determination coefficient test obtained value (R²) of 0.358 or 35.8%, the condition illustrates that the cultural relationship of the organization (X₁), work environment (X₂), work motivation (X₃) to job satisfaction (Y)

is 0.358 or 35.8%. The remaining 64.2% of job satisfaction was affected by other factors, in which case the authors were not studied.

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	18.438	2.466		7.475	.000
	Organizational Culture	.470	.068	.583	6.959	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Job Satisfaction

Table 6:- Partial Hypothesis Test Organizational Culture Variables to Job Satisfaction

From the results of the calculation obtained the value of t_{calculation} of organizational culture (X₁) of 6,959 > t_{table} of 1.6616. Thus, H₁ is accepted and based on the value of probability (Sig) 0,000 < 0.05, which means that H₀ is rejected thus a positive relationship between the organizational culture to job satisfaction in PJLP employees of BPAD has happened.

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	24.107	2.831		8.516	.000
	Work Environment	.338	.085	.380	3.988	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Job Satisfaction

Table 7:- Partial Hypothesis Test (t-test) Work Environment on Job Satisfaction

Based on the results in Table 10 calculation obtained the value of t_{calculate} the working environment (X₂) of 3,988 > t_{table} of 1.6616. Thus, H₁ is accepted and based on the value of probability (Sig) 0.000 < 0.05, which means that H₀ is rejected thus there is a positive relationship between the work environment to job satisfaction in PJLP employees of BPAD.

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	23.290	2.609		8.927	.000
	Work Motivation	.370	.079	.434	4.671	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Job Satisfaction

Table 8:- Partial Hypothesis Test Work Motivation on Job Satisfaction

Based on the calculation result obtained the value of t_{calculate} work motivation (X₃) of 4,671 > t_{table} of 1.6616. Thus, H₁ is accepted and based on probability value 0.000 < 0.05, which means that H₀ is rejected thus there is a positive impact of work motivation on job satisfaction in PJLP employees of BPAD.

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1982.166	3	660.722	17.105	.000 ^b
	Residual	3553.792	92	38.628		
	Total	5535.958	95			
a. Dependent Variable: Job satisfaction						
b. Predictors: (Constant), organizational culture, work environment work motivation						

Table 9:- Simultaneous Hypothesis Test

Based on the overall test obtained $F_{count} > F_{table}$ or $(17,105 > 2.70)$, then H_0 is rejected meaning organizational culture (X_1), work environment (X_2), and work motivation (X_3) simultaneously have a positive impact on job satisfaction (Y).

The results of the study indicate that cultural effects can be seen from the calculation of the linear regression coefficient obtained by the equation $Y = 18.438 + 0.470X_1$, the constant of 18,438 states that organizational culture (X_1) is worth 0, then job satisfaction is 18,438.

The coefficient value of 0.470 means that every increase of one unit of organizational culture will provide an increase in job satisfaction of 0.470. The correlation coefficient value is 0.583 which is classified that the relationship between organizational culture and job satisfaction is moderate, meanwhile, the coefficient of determination obtained a value (R^2) of 0.340 or 34% variability of job satisfaction caused by organizational culture. In other words, the influence of culture on job satisfaction was 34%, and the remaining 66% of job satisfaction was influenced by other factors, in which case the authors did not study.

Due to the acquisition of the value of $t_{calculated} > t_{table}$ of 6,959 $> t_{table}$ of 1.6616 and probability value (Sig.) = 0.000 thus partially there is a positive impact between culture on job satisfaction of PJLP employees in BPAD DKI Jakarta Province. It means, if the organizational culture owned by BPAD is good then employee job satisfaction will also increase, and vice versa. The influence of culture on employee job satisfaction is supported study by Fahmi et al. (2022) on organizational culture's positive impact on employee job satisfaction.

Empirical findings prove that work environment influence on job satisfaction can be seen from the calculation of the coefficient of linear regression obtained in equation $Y = 24.107 + 0.338X_2$, the constant of 24,107 states that if the work environment (X_2) is worth 0, then job satisfaction is 24,107. The correlation coefficient obtained a value (r) of 0.380, which means, the relationship between the work environment to job satisfaction is low. The coefficient of determination obtained a value (R^2) of 0.145 or 14.5%, the variability of job satisfaction because of the work environment. In other words, the contribution of work environment on job satisfaction (is 0.145 or 14.5%. The remaining 85.5% of job satisfaction was affected by other factors, in which case the authors were not studied.

Since the table's t_{count} value of 3,988 $> t_{table}$ is 1.6616, and the probability value (Sig.) = 0.000, there is a partially positive effect of the work environment on job satisfaction. Empirical findings are supported by studies by Wibowo et al. (2022) showed the physical and immaterial work environment has a positive impact on job satisfaction.

Empirical evidence research finds that work motivation influences job satisfaction can be found through the calculation of the linear regression coefficient. obtained equation $Y = 23,290 + 0.370X_3$, the constant of 23,290 states that if the motivation of work (X_3) is worth 0, then job satisfaction is 23,290. The correlation coefficient obtained a value (r) of 0.434 and according to the table of interpretation of the coefficient of entry correlation in quadrant 0. 40-0. 599, this means that the relationship between motivation to job satisfaction is moderate. The coefficient of determination obtained a value (R^2) of 0.188 or 18.8%, the variability of job satisfaction is caused by work motivation. In other words, the contribution from work motivation to job satisfaction amounted to 0.188 or 18.8% of which the remaining 81.2% of job satisfaction was influenced by other factors, in which case the authors were not studied. Empirical evidence that motivation affects job satisfaction is supported by studies by Saluy et al. (2021) found that work motivation positive impact on job satisfaction.

Multiple linear regression model estimation obtained from Equation $Y = 15,911 + 0.367X_1 + 0.070X_2 + 0.123X_3$, constant of 15,911 states that if organizational culture, environment, and motivation. If the value is 0, then job satisfaction is 15,911. Coefficient $b_1 = 0.367$, meaning that if the organizational culture value increases by 1 score then organizational culture affects the increase in job satisfaction by 0.367 scores assuming other variables are constant in value. Coefficient $b_2 = 0.070 X_2$, meaning that if the work environment value increases by 1 score then the work environment variable affects the increase in job satisfaction by a 0.070 score assuming other variables are constant values. Coefficient $b_3 = 0.123X_3$, meaning that if the value of motivation increases by 1 score then the work motivation variable affects increasing job satisfaction by 0.123 scores assuming other variables are constant in value. The correlation coefficient obtained a value (r) of 0.598 and by the table of interpretation of the correlation coefficient 0.40 – 0.599, this means that the cultural relationship of the organization (X_1), the work environment (X_2) and the motivation of work (X_3), to job satisfaction (Y) is moderate. The coefficient of double determination obtained of 0.358 or 35.8%, this means that the variability of job satisfaction that occurs is influenced by culture, environment, and motivation to job satisfaction of 35.8%. The simultaneous hypothesis test obtained the value $F_{calculated}$ by 17,105 and F_{table} of 2.70, because the value of $F_{calculated} > F_{table}$, then H_0 was rejected and which means there is a positive influence between cultures, environment, and motivation together with job satisfaction.

V. CONCLUSION

The conclusion from the research results is that Organizational culture, work environment, and motivation have a positive effect on job satisfaction. Culture has the greatest influence on job satisfaction 0.583 or 58.3%, while work motivation only contributes as much as 38%. And the three variables together affect job satisfaction by 0.598 or 59.8%. Culture has the greatest influence on job satisfaction because the culture in BPAD is very strong and very important for employees in running the organization well which can increase job satisfaction. Organizational culture has the greatest influence on job satisfaction because the organizational culture in BPAD is very strong and very important for employees to carry out their work well which can improve job satisfaction. The environment also has the smallest effect on job satisfaction, but that does not mean that it is simply forgotten, a good environment can support employees in their work, and the work motivation of employees needs to be considered so that employee job satisfaction can be maintained. I suggest that for further research it is necessary to see how the impact of other research variables that aren't discussed in this paper on employee satisfaction, which may not be seen well by this paper like workers' compensation and top management commitment variables so that they can increase the treasury of knowledge, especially those related to with human resource development.

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